

**PECULIARITIES OF UZBEKISTAN'S FOREIGN POLICY IN THE CENTRAL
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Abstract: It is known that Uzbekistan is a country of strategic importance in Central Asia. At the same time, the foreign political and diplomatic relations of our country with Asian and European countries help to further strengthen the political position of Uzbekistan. On the other hand, the foreign policy of Uzbekistan under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev experienced significant changes, in foreign policy more emphasis was placed on the policy of active cooperation and constructive diplomacy. -2030" project "We can see that a new political system is being formed, moving from the strategy of actions to the direction of development strategy. The main goals of this reform program are to establish stronger relations with the Central Asian neighbors of Uzbekistan, to jointly solve regional problems and to contribute to a more harmonious and prosperous Central Asia. In addition, the influence of our country in the region and on the world scale has increased, the world has increased confidence in New Uzbekistan and the desire to establish political and economic relations with our country, the policy of "good neighborliness" is being carried out in relation to neighboring countries, trade and the rapid development of cultural and humanitarian relations is a clear proof that the "spirit of Central Asia" has appeared in world political science.

Keywords: "Global Uzbekistan", strategy, "Spirit of Central Asia", international policy, Eurasian economic policy, diversified economy, SCO, OSCE, cyber security, CIS, landscape, Mazari Sharif, Peshovar, economic corridor.

1.ENTRY AND VALIDITY. Today, the Republic of Uzbekistan is entering a new promising stage, i.e. the period of the Third Renaissance. The increasing role and importance of Uzbekistan in world politics, as well as the efforts being made to build a new Uzbekistan we can Uzbekistan's foreign policy has undergone serious changes due to the need for a more open and flexible approach to international relations. These changes include reforms in the system of the

Ministry of Foreign Affairs, its foreign missions abroad and relations with local entities. Although the long-term results of these changes are yet to be seen, they are the first step towards Uzbekistan's position as a liberalizing foreign country. The government's efforts to support the constructive development function are important in persuading foreign partners and promoting Uzbekistan's integration into the world community. The reforms carried out under the policy of good neighborliness of Uzbekistan, and the attempt to establish cooperation and peaceful relations with Afghanistan, which is currently in an unstable situation, are proof of the existence of long-standing cultural and civilizational ties between the two countries. Afghanistan's geographical proximity to Uzbekistan directly affects the national security of Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan believes that Afghanistan has the potential to create new opportunities for regional cooperation. The specific features of Uzbekistan's foreign policy and the fact that it is based on practical cooperation are reflected in the principles of the "Strategy of Actions to the Strategy of Development" and the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy.

METHODS AND LEVEL OF EDUCATION. The article utilizes theoretical-methodological, statistical analysis, and systematization approaches, as well as comparative and systematic analysis methods.

RESEARCH AND RESULTS. In a global environment experiencing a new wave of innovative development, our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's initiatives have taken another step towards the realization of the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategic project, marking a new phase known as the formation of "Global Uzbekistan." This strategy is the normative document aimed at realizing the vision of "New Uzbekistan," encompassing five directions and 100 objectives. It(Lex.uz.,Decree,2023) emphasizes the ideological and moral foundation, distinctive creativity for our people, and the effective implementation of our broad-scale reforms (Sh. Mirziyoyev, 2021). In contemporary international relations, Uzbekistan is transitioning to a new national and legal system, recognizing human rights as a fundamental value, forming the "individual-society-state" paradigm. President Mirziyoyev's previously outlined goals in the "Development Strategy 2022-2026" align with these principles. The logical continuation of the "Development Strategy – Strategy of Actions" defines the essence of the "New Uzbekistan".

As outlined by Akmal Saidov (2023), the ongoing changes in development necessitate two new priority directions in the Development Strategy, focusing on spiritual development and addressing global challenges faced by Uzbekistan on the world stage. Uzbekistan continues to

actively participate in UN activities, serving as the singular universal organization responsible for ensuring international peace and security, aiding stable development in the era of rapid globalization. Our country strengthens cooperation with European Security and Cooperation Organization, Shanghai Cooperation Organization, and Organization of Islamic Cooperation to enhance comprehensive collaboration in addressing contemporary challenges and threats (Mirziyoyev, Our joint efforts should truly feel the impact of our actions).Uzbekistan's policy is aimed at expanding international cooperation, solidifying relations with regional powers, various organizations, and Western states to strengthen its international ties. To achieve these goals, President Mirziyoyev has implemented significant reforms, including:

- **Reassessing relations with neighboring countries:** Initiating high-level visits and summits with Central Asian nations to overcome historical issues and build trust.

- **Greater openness and transparency:** Embracing openness and diplomacy in foreign policy, actively collaborating with international media outlets, and fostering dialogue with the global community (Aminjonov et al., 2019).

- **Regional Integration Focus:** Uzbekistan has actively engaged in Central Asia Regional Economic Cooperation (CAREC) initiatives and projects like the New Silk Road, aiming to enhance regional integration.

- **Attracting Foreign Investments:** Economic reforms in Uzbekistan have attracted direct foreign investments from various countries, improving the investment climate.

- **Cultural Diplomacy Enhancement:** Uzbekistan has organized cultural festivals, exhibitions, and educational exchanges to promote its cultural heritage and strengthen international relations.

The foreign policy changes in Uzbekistan have yielded positive results:

Improved Relations with Neighbors: Strengthened and improved relations with Central Asian nations, leading to increased trade, cultural exchange, and regional collaboration.

Diversification of Economy: Successful diversification of the economy through attracting foreign investments, developing new sectors such as tourism and IT, reducing dependence on cotton exports, and creating new job opportunities.

Enhanced Regional Relations: Uzbekistan has fostered cultural exchange, educational collaborations, and business partnerships, fostering understanding and cooperation among nations.

Global Challenges and Security: The dynamic regional landscape, influenced by geopolitical shifts and challenges in Afghanistan and China, requires Uzbekistan to continue prioritizing regional stability and safeguarding national interests. In conclusion, Uzbekistan's evolving foreign policy has not only addressed challenges but also opened up new opportunities for economic growth, cultural exchange, and regional collaboration, contributing to global problem-solving and cooperation.

Uzbekistan is navigating significant changes in the global landscape, facing challenges such as climate change, cybersecurity, and the demand for innovative solutions in the digital economy. To effectively address these global issues, Uzbekistan needs to align its foreign policy with international obligations. The internal priorities, like economic development and social prosperity, must harmonize with global responsibilities. Efficient coordination and equitable resource distribution are crucial. To enhance global cooperation and influence, Uzbekistan should play a pivotal role in international affairs, leveraging its geographic position. One crucial aspect of this strategy is the proposal by Uzbekistan's leadership to engage in political dialogue with Afghanistan, fostering regional collaboration and economic interdependence. Uzbekistan and Afghanistan, with deep historical ties, share a foundation of strong cultural and civilizational values. The historical connection between Uzbekistan and Afghanistan has been influenced by political boundaries rather than the voluntary formation of these states. Despite their separate existence, they were politically divided and considered part of a single region. The ongoing development in Afghanistan is crucial for Uzbekistan, given their close geographical proximity. The national security threats and the spectrum of challenges directly affect Uzbekistan's collaborative efforts and interests in the entire region. The security of Afghanistan is integral to the stability of the entire region, and Uzbekistan's proactive approach demonstrates its commitment to establishing a secure and prosperous neighborhood. Tashkent's stability is directly linked to the security of Afghanistan, making Uzbekistan a key stakeholder in regional development. President Mirziyoyev's administration not only focuses on immediate foreign policy goals but also considers the evolving landscape to shape a sustainable external policy. Additionally, Uzbekistan's economic and trade collaborations, particularly with Tashkent as the

central hub, aim to maximize the transportation capabilities of Central Asia and other countries. The strategic vision includes the formation of the "China-Central Asia-West Asia" economic corridor, reflecting Uzbekistan's commitment to regional economic integration. Moreover, the government is exploring the construction of the Mazari Sharif-Kabul-Peshawar railway, providing an additional outlet to Pakistani ports. In summary, Uzbekistan's foreign policy initiatives are strategically aligning with the global changes and regional dynamics, focusing on economic partnerships, security, and collaborative regional development. The engagement with Afghanistan and the emphasis on regional economic corridors showcase Uzbekistan's commitment to fostering stability and prosperity in the broader Central Asian context.

The "Development Strategy" is at the center of the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy, announced for public discussion. The strategy encompasses significant goals for the country's development, particularly emphasizing the policy rooted in the first of the fifth top-priority goals – the policy of creating an "Secure and Peaceful State," continuing and further strengthening a clear, pragmatic, and active foreign policy to enhance Uzbekistan's position in the Central Asian region ("Uzbekistan-2030" strategy, 2023). The strategy "Advancing the New Uzbekistan" has been defined with five priorities and 100 specific objectives over seven years. To implement this, a total of 252.2 billion USD is allocated (Saidov, 2023).

The key directions of the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy include: Establishing an education, healthcare, and social protection system that meets the needs of the population and international standards (44 goals).

Ensuring the well-being of the population through sustainable economic growth (17 goals).

Creating favorable ecological conditions for the population, including efficient water resource management (12 goals).

Establishing a just and modern state that serves the people, ensuring the rule of law (16 goals).

Continuation of activities to transform the country into a secure and peaceful state, implementing open, pragmatic, and active foreign policy, and strengthening the country's security and defense capabilities (11 goals).

The President's decree on the strategy emphasizes the need to update the fundamental directions of developing Uzbekistan in the constitutionally-legal framework. It outlines the necessity of advancing amendments and innovations to bring reforms to a new level (A.Saidov, 2023).As highlighted in the document, all state bodies and organizations are tasked with implementing and achieving the strategic goals. The new development strategy of Uzbekistan shifts from the strategy of actions to the strategy of development. It places special importance on comprehensive and logical development in various sectors, aiming to achieve specific results in key priority areas. The strategy incorporates broad measures, including developing civil society, ensuring the rule of law, implementing constitutional reforms, enhancing the national economy, promoting a strong social policy, fostering spirituality, resolving global issues, passing laws and regulations to address security challenges, and addressing foreign policy matters. Within these overarching goals, the President's "For the Sake of Human Dignity" initiative, presented in the Saylovoldi program, embodies the overall goal of protecting human dignity (Sh.Mirziyoyev, 2021).In this context, it is evident that the ongoing reforms encompassing political, economic, social, cultural, and ecological aspects are not confined solely to the Central Asian region. They also aim to elevate Uzbekistan's status as a legal democratic state, enhancing the dignity of the individual and achieving significant goals on the international stage.

CONCLUSIONS

From the above discussions, several conclusions can be drawn. Firstly, Uzbekistan's foreign policy indicates a clear shift: there is a noticeable shift in attention towards global issues, demonstrating a more pragmatic foreign policy, especially in addressing regional challenges and improving relations with neighboring countries, such as China, Russia, and efforts to maintain balance in the Russia-CIS region. The United States recognizes Uzbekistan as a powerful state in Central Asia, emphasizing a more pragmatic foreign policy focused on resolving regional issues and enhancing relations with regional states. This is a significant shift, as unresolved issues with neighboring countries could potentially hinder the economic development of Uzbekistan and the Central Asian region as a whole.Secondly, the efforts to establish and strengthen cooperation with the currently unstable state of Afghanistan are considered a priority in Uzbekistan's foreign policy. Additionally, collaborations with international organizations, such as the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE), Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), and the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), play a crucial role in Uzbekistan's development.

These broad political, economic, and social decision-making initiatives, along with visionary goals and strategic plans, are contributing significantly to the country's development. These extensive political, economic, social, cultural, and ecological reforms are not limited to the Central Asian region. They are designed to elevate Uzbekistan's status as a legal democratic state, fostering human dignity and achieving significant goals on the international stage. In conclusion, the ongoing transformations in Uzbekistan's foreign policy are evident in its pragmatic approach, addressing global challenges, building stronger relations with neighboring countries, and prioritizing regional stability. This shift is crucial for the economic development of Uzbekistan and the Central Asian region, and it aligns with the country's overarching goals outlined in strategic documents like the "Development Strategy" and "Uzbekistan-2030."

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